

Coypus and dragons - The Evolunionist Pharage

1. General Information

- **Performance Title:** Coypus and Dragons - The Evolutionist Pharage
- **Main Contact:** Domenico Cipriani a.k.a. Lucretio
- **Additional Performers:**
- **Performance Type:** Algorave

2. Abstract

A 30 minutes live coding performance for Pharo, Kyma and Processing, exploring the fitness of rhythms, bass and harmonies in the Algorave environment. A social experiment with euclidean geometries, hexadecimal beats and post-jungle patterns drifting from sparse broken drums and essential scaled-down soulful chords to bass-driven percussive timelines and recursive frequency modulated quirks.

Heavily influenced by the sound from South London and Detroit the performance is designed as a live coding extension of “Multidimensional Wobbles - The Minimalist Capygarage” performed at the Kyma International Symposium of 2019 at Daedong College in Buon, South Korea.

Coypu is the package we have been developing for programming music on-the-fly with Pharo. It is also a common rodent on the banks of the river Brenta, imported in the 80 for fur farming that widespread when it was released in the environment after the end of the yuppies era.

The Dragons have be chosen to symbolically dance with the Coypus as an homage to the People Republic of China and its traditions; they will be represented through an heavy use of Chines pentatonic scales.

3. Video and/or Audio Material

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yBK0UpalBfk&t=353s>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pgjxpYaxfA&t=416s>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=q18GjMGshQY>

4. Program Note

A 25 minutes uptempo, danceable rhythm and blues performance. All the sounds generated by Symbolic Sound Kyma, and programmed on-the-fly with Coypu, the live coding package for Pharo. Visuals pre-programmed in Processing and iconically controlled live with Kyma through the Open Sound Protocol.

5. Artist(s) Biography

Domenico Cipriani a.k.a. Lucretio has been releasing raw minimalist dance music for more than a decade. With his many monikers and groups (including collaborations with Blawan and Objekt) he has released more than 100 vinyls and performed all around Europe, including Berghain, Tresor, Fabric, Zukunft, Rex, just to name a few. His label Restoration (co-founded with Marieu) has played an active role in the vinyl resurgence of the late 2000.

After his graduation the S.A.E. Institute of Barcelona, he has further developed his research on social semiotic with an M.A. in Linguistics at the University of Padova, focusing on an

evolutionary approach to explaining language change. He has discovered Smalltalk with Symbolic Sound Kyma in 2016. In 2019, he presented at the >>Sonic Experiments<< festival at the ZKM an interactive performance based on network distributed Open Sound Control. He has been live coding with Kyma and Pharo since April 2020.